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IMPROVING TIMELY ACCESS TO CARE IN A COMMUNITY HEALTH CLINIC

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

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By

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ABSTRACT

The ability of patients to consistently schedule appointments in a timely manner with their primary care provider (PCP) is a common problem plaguing many primary care offices within the United States (US). Timely access and continuity of care with the PCP has been associated with better health outcomes, longevity, and decreased healthcare costs. This business plan will propose a budget for a new federally qualified health center (FQHC) location outside of Albuquerque, New Mexico. The Six-Sigma quality improvement process will be used to design a new provider scheduling template to try to improve timely access and continuity of care with a PCP. Proposed measures and the recommended control charts used for monitoring the quality improvement process were identified and the rationale for their use discussed. Recommendations for future quality improvement projects regarding timely access and continuity of care will also be made.

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BACKGROUND

The Problem of Access in the United States

The United States is struggling to provide timely access to health care and continuity of care among primary care providers (Corscadden et al., 2018). Timely access has been defined as the ability of patients to obtain an appointment that is suitable to their schedule and addressing their healthcare needs (Ringel, Melnick, Setodji, Reddick, & Paddock, 2019). Continuity of care is a patient's ability to see the assigned PCP instead of seeing a different PCP in the healthcare setting. Continuity of care is represented by the percentage of assigned patients seen by the assigned PCP (Institute for Healthcare Improvement [IHI], 2019a). Timely access to care and continuity of care have been associated with lower mortality, improved patient experiences, improved health outcomes, and decreased costs (Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality [AHRQ], 2013; Maarsingh, Henry, van de Ven, & Deeg, 2016). These outcomes make addressing access imperative for healthcare organizations.

An Increasing Need for Access

The challenge of offering timely and consistent access to care is becoming more problematic as the population ages and the number of PCPs decreases (Auerbach et al., 2013). As the country ages, the number of individuals older than 65 will exceed 83.7 million by the year 2050 (Ortman, Velkoff, & Hogan, 2014). It is anticipated that there may be fewer physicians to meet the needs of an aging population due to PCPs who are retiring and medical school graduates choosing specialties other than family or internal medicine (Pettersen, Liaw, Tran, & Bazemore, 2015). Fewer medical school graduates

are choosing to practice family or internal medicine due to reimbursement concerns and a perception of higher workloads (Petterson et al., 2015).

The Affordable Care Act (ACA) increased access to healthcare services for many individuals during a time when the number of PCPs was not sufficient to cover the number of new patients entering the healthcare system (Miller & Wherry, 2017). The imbalance between need and supply is especially prevalent in medically underserved communities where the wait times for an appointment can be three or more months (Heild, 2019; New Mexico Health Care Workforce Committee, 2018; Ramos, Coughlin, Weiss, & Long, 2016).

Aim

The aim of this project was to develop a business plan for a new federally qualified health center (FQHC) located in a rural area of Central New Mexico. The goal of the FQHC will be to provide timely access and continuity of care for an underserved community in Sandoval County.

Sandoval County's Demographics

In 2018, there were 145,179 persons living in Sandoval County, and the population increased by 13,559 persons over the past eight years (U.S. Census Bureau, 2018b). There are approximately 37.4 people per square mile (University of New Mexico Sandoval Regional Medical Center [SRMC], 2019). For reference, Bernalillo County, where Albuquerque (the most populous city in New Mexico), is located, has 2,907.6 people per square mile (U.S. Census Bureau, 2018a). Sandoval County has 12 Native American reservations, meaning it houses the state's largest population of Native Americans (University of New Mexico SRMC, 2019). The Native American population

is at risk for increased chronic disease prevalence and poorer health outcomes (Adakai, Sandoval-Rosario, Asere-Manygoats, Allison, Greenlund, & Barbour, 2018). Improving access to care in the area is important in improving health outcomes of the population.

In Sandoval County, 15.3% of the population is living at the poverty level. This percentage is higher than that of the nation, which is 11.8% (United States Census Bureau, 2019). Only 9.7% of the population under the age of 65 is insured, and 17.1% is over 65 (University of New Mexico SRMC, 2019; U.S. Census Bureau, 2018b). The ethnic breakdown of the county is 43.1% White, 39.4% Hispanic, 14% Native American, 2.7% Black, and 1.7% Asian. Most people in the county are minorities, and 16.7% speak Spanish as their primary language (University of New Mexico SRMC, 2019).

Access to Care in Sandoval County

In 2018, the average monthly percentage of enrollees in Medicaid in Sandoval County was 31.9% compared to 22.7% of the U.S. population (University of New Mexico SRMC, 2019). Between 2013 and 2017, 29.4% of the county's population was without a designated PCP. Despite an increase in the number of insured patients through Medicaid expansion, approximately 8% to 16% of members of ethnic minorities are not insured (University of New Mexico SRMC, 2019). Figure 1 shows the distance between FQHC locations (white plus signs within green circles), school-based clinics (yellow flags), and the New Mexico Department of Health Public Health Offices (red stars with white centers). Inhabitants of Sandoval County who earned between \$5,000 and \$30,000 a year spent over 24% of their earnings on transportation (University of New Mexico SRMC, 2019). Transportation and drive time are barriers to accessing primary health care in the county.

Figure 1. Map of Sandoval and Bernalillo counties. Proposed clinic location represented by blue triangle. Yellow flags are school-based clinics, white plus signs in green circle are FQHC's, and red stars with white centers are New Mexico Public Health Centers. Map taken and modified with permission from <https://www.arcgis.com/home/webmap/viewer.html?webmap=70b78b8ff44047d7ae6553442e448319>

Chronic Disease Burden and Identified Health Needs

Over 23% of New Mexico's patient population (1.6 million persons) has more than one chronic disease, such as coronary artery disease, asthma, depression, anxiety, substance abuse disorder, arthritis, renal disease, or diabetes (New Mexico Department of Health, 2018). In Sandoval County, 9.2% of adults have been diagnosed with asthma. The leading cause of death and disability in the county is attributable to chronic diseases (University of New Mexico SRMC, 2019). Death rates associated with diabetes and stroke are higher in Sandoval County compared to the entire state population. The U.S.

diabetes mortality rate was highest between 2015 and 2017 at 71.2 persons per 100,000 among Native Americans living in New Mexico. The statistics indicate a need for improved chronic disease prevention and management. Improved health literacy through improved access and continuity of care can also help to improve outcomes (Hudson, Rikard, Staiculescu, & Edison, 2018).

The University of New Mexico SRMC (2019) conducted a community health needs assessment (CHNA) in 2019 identifying top healthcare needs of focus in Sandoval County. The CHNA was a requirement set forth by the implementation of the ACA and must be completed every three years by hospitals for them to continue receiving federal funding. The CHNA identifies local community needs and ensures local hospitals align with these needs when developing and providing services. In 2019, the top priorities for targeted improvement identified by the SRMC CHNA for Sandoval County were expanding mental health services through expansion of behavioral health outpatient clinics and crisis intervention; improving access to health care through expansion of primary, specialty and trauma services; and improving chronic disease preventive measures and management specifically for diabetes, breast, and colon cancer screenings, which should reduce hospital readmissions.

Lack of Equitable Access to Healthcare

Sandoval County has a high number of uninsured patients (University of New Mexico SRMC, 2019). Lack of insurance has been shown to contribute to delays in care due to the cost of healthcare services, resulting in preventable hospitalizations (Kaiser Family Foundation [KFF], 2018). Care of the uninsured has been associated with less diagnostic testing and therapeutic treatments and increased mortality rates (KFF, 2018).

Approximately 31.9% of patients in Sandoval County are insured through Medicaid, and most are minorities (University of New Mexico SRMC, 2019). There is a lack of equity in access to healthcare services among minorities (Institute of Medicine, 2003; Schpero et al., 2017). Schpero et al. (2017) found that, even when the presence of insurance coverage was controlled for, minorities were less likely to receive high value health care and experienced poorer health outcomes than Whites. Low income minorities have a higher prevalence of chronic disease and tend to delay health care, which increases their risk of morbidity and mortality (Artiga, Foutz, Cornachione, & Garfield, 2016; Bauer, Briss, Goodman, & Bowman, 2014; Price, Khubchandani, McKinney, & Braun, 2013). It is imperative to consistently provide timely access to health care to high-risk populations to reduce disease burden, hospitalizations, mortality, and cost of care (AHRQ, 2013).

Timely Access and Continuity of Care as Quality Metrics

Clinics that primarily care for Medicaid-insured patients must adhere to their state's human services department (HSD) or equivalent published timely access regulations, which are based on the patients' healthcare needs at the time of the request for an appointment. New Mexico's HSD (2014) regulations state that patients with primary care urgent requests must be seen within 24 hours, those with non-urgent but symptomatic primary care requests must be seen within 14 business days, and asymptomatic, routine, primary care appointment requests should take place within 30 days. These regulations were designed to give the term "timely access" a defined timeframe for healthcare organizations to follow. Noticeably, although they define the time standard of when urgent and non-urgent visits should occur, there is not a standard

for continuity of care. The IHI (2019a) suggested a goal greater than 80% of patients being scheduled with their PCP for the continuity of care metric. Ideally, greater than 80% of patients scheduled daily in primary care should be scheduled with their PCP and not another provider.

Problem Statement

The ability of a healthcare organization to provide timely access and continuity of care for patients pertains to its ability to provide equity in health care, which is especially important for Medicaid-insured patients and their social determinants of health (SDOH). According to Mason, Gardner, Outlaw and O'Grady (2016), the SDOH are a person's socioeconomic and political characteristics that may include their socioeconomic status, race, and inequity in health care, which can have longstanding impact on their health. There are multiple factors influencing the issues of timely access and continuity of care for patients, including their SDOH. Factors strongly affecting patients' timely access and continuity of care include the nation's increased need for access, an aging and medically complex population, lack of equity of care, a lack of medical graduates seeking work in primary care, a medically complex population, clinic scheduling practices, and increased cost of health care resulting in medical payment reform (Brandenburg, Gabow, Steele, Toussaint, & Tyson, 2015). With many changes occurring in the nation's medical landscape, it is imperative that primary care offices engage in novel ways of meeting patients' needs to increase the value of care they receive. Because of the increasing complexities required to care for patients, restructuring how patients gain access to their PCP through scheduling practices should be considered.

Theoretical Framework: Six Sigma

Theoretical frameworks provide the infrastructure for a conceptually sound project (Roush, 2019). The Six Sigma framework was employed to guide the development and implementation of a new scheduling process and provider template within an FQHC.

The Six Sigma framework is employed to guide innovating practice changes such as the one proposed by this author. Six Sigma is a methodology initiated in 1987 by Motorola (Marr, 2018). Six Sigma is a methodology to reduce variations in processes and emphasizes elimination of defects to increase system productivity (Marr, 2018). As shown in Figure 2, Six Sigma identifies six steps to improve quality, collectively termed DMAIC: define, measure, analyze, improve, and control (Graves, 2014).

Figure 2. Six Sigma DMAIC construct. Conceptualization for improving access and continuity of care (adapted from Kubiak, 2014).

Define

During the define step, a problem is identified, and a business case is created (Kubiak, 2014). According to George, Rowlands, Price, and Maxey (2005), the define step is the initial plan for why and how the innovation will be implemented. For this business plan, it is recommended that the define step be operationalized by engaging stakeholders in recognition of the problem (e.g. access and continuity), creating a team, conducting a value stream map, creating a Gantt chart, and a project charter. A value stream map is a one-page visual depiction of the current processes which can be developed and should reflect the amount of time for each process step, usually in minutes, that a customer spends in value-added or nonvalue-added time (Langley et al., 2009). A Gantt chart is a project planning tool typically created using a spreadsheet and places the timeline with the months along the X axis and the various milestones for the project to be accomplished on the Y axis (Langley et al., 2009). The charter typically includes the problem statement, the overarching goal, timeline, team, and the financial targets (George et al., 2005).

Measure

The next step is measure (George et al., 2005). During the measure step, baseline data are collected and analyzed so that performance goals can be set (Kubiak, 2014). Baseline data should be collected related to patients' wait times to see their PCP for the various types of visits (urgent, non-urgent, and routine) and continuity. Lastly, the project development team should create clear operational definitions for access and continuity by consensus. The team should determine the data collection process and the tools necessary for tracking processes (George et al., 2005). The data should be recorded on spreadsheets,

tracked on run charts and, eventually, control charts. Run charts are graphs used to track data points that are serially collected and can show either a stable or uncontrolled process (Provost & Murray, 2011). After 20 data points are collected, the run charts should transition to a control chart for more accurate data evaluation and analysis (Provost & Murray, 2011).

Analyze

During the analyze step, the access and continuity data are analyzed in more detail (George et al., 2005). The analyze step should be operationalized by reviewing the value-added and non-value-added processes related to the scheduling processes for the patient. A value stream map has already been conducted at another clinic site and was used to provide overall guidance for this project's scheduling plan. Non-value-added time for patients was found to be caused by inefficiencies at the centralized scheduling center, delays at the clinics' front desk (mostly related to check-in and insurance processing), and patient flow in the clinic. This business plan proposes a scheduling plan for this project's FQHC to optimize timely access to appointments and meet the goals for continuity of care.

Improve

The improve step is where implementation occurs. Creativity is important during this step, as potential solutions may be very different from planned processes (George et al., 2005). For this project, the improve process will be operationalized by revisiting the value stream map to assess how scheduling affects downstream processes. The practice change related to scheduling will be created and implemented by the team. An announcement of the change will take place at a staff meeting the week before the change

occurs, so all staff are aware of the new process. The practice change will be executed with documentation of the process and identification of lessons learned along the way for later review by the team. Analysis of the data will support whether the change is successful.

Control

The control step is the last step in the Six Sigma model (Graves, 2014). If the implemented process is successful, the team may decide to implement the new process throughout the organization. The control step will be operationalized by documenting the transition to the new process with review of the before and after data metrics. The control step will include an evaluation of the sustainability of the new process. There should be support provided to staff to facilitate the change so that staff do not revert to old practices. Leadership should monitor the implementation and engage in a planned periodic review every three months. The fiscal impact will be reviewed monthly after implementation of the change.

In summary, the Six Sigma model will provide the structure for this business plan aimed at improving patient access and continuity of care. Even though each step is operationalized by specific processes, flexibility is important through each stage. According to Graves (2014), if a quick change in a process can be made that meets patients' needs, then, with consensus, the change should happen. The process should require the effort and input of many team members, so it is important to consistently work together to improve processes.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The purpose of this project is to develop a business plan for an FQHC to optimize access and continuity of care for an underserved population in Sandoval County, New Mexico. This review of literature summarizes the information related to factors affecting access to care, results of lack of access, methods used to improve access, and models to improve scheduling. A literature review specific to the use of six sigma and improving access is also discussed. The search engines used for the literature review are PubMed, CINAHL, and EBSCO. A few seminal articles related to the topics of interest were also included if they provided foundational information for the project.

Factors Affecting Access to Care and Continuity of Care

In primary care, timely access has been defined as the ability of the patient to obtain an appointment in a timely manner suitable to and fitting the healthcare need of the patient (Ringel et al., 2019). Continuity of care is a patient's ability to consistently see the assigned PCP, usually represented by the daily percentage of patients seen by their assigned PCP (IHI, 2019a). The assignation of a patient to the PCP results in a PCP empanelment, which is usually a mix between the patient's preferred provider and the provider who last saw the patient within the prior 18 months (Weir, Page, & Newton, 2016).

The issue of patient access to primary care appointments became more problematic for many medical practices with the implementation of the ACA in 2010 (Okoro et al., 2017). Due to the influx of millions of newly insured patients and the inadequate number of healthcare providers, there have been longer wait times for patients to see their PCP (Miller & Wherry, 2017). Longer wait times have been associated with

decreased perceived quality of care, confidence in the provider, and patient satisfaction (Bleustein et al., 2014).

Patients who have complicated medical conditions require prompt care to reduce further complications, mortality, and cost (AHRQ, 2013). This is one factor influencing the need for timely access and continuity of care. An asthmatic patient who can quickly access care with their PCP at the clinic level may not need to be seen in the emergency department due to escalated asthmatic symptoms requiring emergent care. Furthermore, research supports that timely access and continuity of care reduces risk of hospitalization, mortality, and cost of care (Hollander & Kadlec, 2015; Hussey et al., 2014; Kohnke & Zielinski, 2017; Maarsingh et al., 2016; Shin et al., 2014). Primary care practices should strive to improve timely access and continuity of care because it serves patients and may improve patient outcomes and clinic reimbursement.

Systems Redesign and Improving Timely Access and Continuity of Care

Research demonstrates that a multifactorial approach to care improves access (Brandenburg et al., 2015). Brandenburg et al. (2015) identified three key factors affecting access: systems thinking, system redesign, and respect for patients accessing their healthcare providers. Organizations that have had success in improving timely access incorporated change in all three of these areas.

Systems thinking and systems redesign are deductive approaches to solving a problem which assumes the solution to the problem of access has multiple contributors (Mele, Pels, & Polese, 2010). The problem of providing patients timely access to health care is a systems problem (Brandenburg et al., 2015). Brandenburg et al. (2015) noted that methods for improving timely access and maximizing health care involves the

redesign of the electronic health record (EHR). The EHR was designed to gather data regarding patient characteristics and allow providers to align their care to the patient's needs (Gabow & Goodman, 2015). For this author's project, the effective use of the EHR for scheduling will be a key component of the practice change. The EHR will provide scheduling data related to access and the PCP's patients need for continuity of care in the form of the weekly percentage of assigned patients seen by the PCP.

Similarly, Gavriloff, Ostrowski-Delahanty and Oldfield (2017) used data collected from the EHR to improve patient scheduling and decrease wait times in a pediatric specialty outpatient practice. They tracked when patients arrived at their center and found that patients arrived in higher volumes during specific times in the day, which increased wait times. They determined the busiest days of the week and calculated patient arrivals for every 30 minutes during the day. The authors redesigned the schedule to address the high volume of patients, which was identified as a level-loading intervention called a "Heijunka," a Lean Six Sigma term. The redesigned schedule helped regulate patient flow during the busiest times of the day. As a result of the schedule change, there was a significant decrease in patient wait time after check-in at the office. The number of patients seen daily did increase, which increased revenue. One limitation of the study was that it took place over a 2-month period, which may not have been long enough to capture the true effect of the intervention. Gavriloff et al. (2017) were not able to reduce the indirect wait time, which could be due to the project having taken place in a specialty practice wherein providers function independently. It is possible that, using a similar team scheduling method may help decrease the indirect wait time in the project location.

Sometimes, the clinic itself may need a redesign to facilitate better patient flow and provide the space needed to accommodate providers and patients comfortably (Brown-Johnson et al., 2019). After significant baseline data collection which included qualitative surveys for patients and providers, Brown-Johnson et al. (2019) engaged their clinic in a total transformation from the design of the clinic to redesign of their primary teams: a physician, nurse practitioner, and four medical assistants. The clinic engaged three of these teams to care for 10,000 patients. They saw improvement in quality of care, patient and provider satisfaction, and productivity.

Patient Centered Care Improves Timely Access to Care and Continuity

The review of literature revealed several factors affecting patient's perceptions of timely access and continuity of care. One contributor to timely access and continuity of care was patient-centered communication including providing patients with access to their preferred method of communication. D'Avolio, Strumpf, Feldman, Mitchell, and Rebholz (2013) conducted a mixed-methods study in an elderly, low socioeconomic status population to investigate the reasons for seeking care at an emergency department. Three themes were identified as contributing to inappropriate use of the emergency room: lack of timely access to care at the primary care level, problems with communication (e.g., never receiving a call back or navigation of the phone tree), and inefficiencies within the clinic itself. A combination of the patients' older age and inability to navigate the technology necessary to speak with office staff contributed most to the lack of timely access and continuity of care.

A systematic review by Ansell, Crispo, Simard, and Bjerre (2017) suggested that alternative forms of electronic communication such as emailing the PCP and telephone

consultation helped improve access in some studies. Reid et al. (2009) conducted a prospective, quasi-experimental study over 12 months wherein they implemented a patient-centered medical home model (PCMH) that increased patient access to the provider via email and billable telephone visits. Although Reid et al. (2009) reduced in-person visits, the in-person visits were typically longer than before the change which patients seemed to enjoy. Although health-specific patient outcomes were not mentioned, emergency room visits decreased over the 12 months of the study. Patient and provider satisfaction increased post-change with no associated increased costs. These studies by Reid et al. (2009), D'Avolio et al. (2013) and Ansell et al. (2017) highlight the importance of providing patients with a patient-centered approach for communication.

Another contributor to timely access and continuity of care was the patient's knowledge about personal health problems. Barry et al. (2006) conducted a study regarding the perceptions of timely access to care among patients and providers in Canada. Providers indicated that patients' perceptions regarding their need for an appointment were not as urgent as the patients believed. The most common reasons for requesting an urgent appointment were chronic stomach pain, chronic knee pain, routine diabetes care, and elevated cholesterol. Although the patient and provider often differed in their perceived urgency for an appointment, they did agree that wheezing asthmatic patients, ankle pain and injury, and a sore throat constituted an urgent appointment. Perhaps with improving timely access at this business plan's proposed clinic, providers can work with patients to improve health literacy.

The need for timely access is driven by the patients, and this is based most importantly on their knowledge of their problems and their perception of the urgency of their healthcare needs. The review of literature revealed that having a nurse triage system may help patients determine if their need warrants a same-day appointment, an emergency department visit, or a visit at a later time. A nurse triage system may reduce the patient's wait time on the phone since it bypasses clinic phones, therefore improving patient communication (Brandenburg et al., 2015). This business plan for the proposed clinic involves hiring two registered nurses (RNs), one of whom can perform triage while the other is performing other clinic duties.

Patients request to see their provider, but how this occurs depends on the provider who serves them. Advanced access scheduling provides patients the ability to see their provider the day they call, but, when the demand outpaces the supply, patients are placed with another provider or seek care outside of the organization (Murray & Berwick, 2003). Seeing an alternate provider may result in a need for another appointment, as urgent care centers and emergency departments usually refer patients back to their PCP. Murray and Berwick (2003) acknowledge variations in patient demand as a driver of the access problem. The variation in demand and its negative effect on timely access and continuity of care might be partially alleviated by the implementation of a team scheduling method wherein at least one member of a primary care team can consistently see their group's patients. One provider's schedule could be composed of mostly advanced access (Murray & Berwick, 2003) or assigned a lighter patient load to take on the patients who need access as the day progresses. This business plan for the proposed clinic will use a

combination of advanced access and open access scheduling to improve timely access and continuity of care.

Third Next Available Appointment

According to Murray and Berwick (2003), the best measure of a provider's available access is use of the "third next available physical examination" (p. 1038), because this appointment type is usually scheduled last. This appointment is a sentinel marker for access (measured in days) as originally recommended by the IHI (2019b). The IHI describes the third next available appointment availability as likely not being due to a cancellation and represents a true open appointment, representative of the PCPs true availability. PCPs whose third next available appointment is closer to zero (i.e., patients can receive an appointment with their PCP the day they call for access) have better timely access for their patients, therefore providing better continuity of care. Directly quoted from the first paragraph of the IHI's website on the third next available appointment (2019b), the first three available appointments (for a "new patient physical, routine exam, or return visit exam") should be available the same day. However, the goal for the third next available appointment for a routine physical at the author's place of employment is within two weeks. To improve value-added time to the patients' clinic experience, reducing the wait time to the third next available appointment is necessary. This business plan's scheduling template for the proposed clinic may help to reduce the wait time to the third next available appointment to less than two weeks.

Continuity of Care

The problem of timely access is interconnected with continuity of care (Weir, Page, & Newton, 2016). When the demand for appointments is not met with a sufficient

supply, timely access with the PCP is delayed resulting in decreased continuity of care (Balasubramanian & Rossi, 2018; Weir, Page, & Newton, 2016). Patients may see another provider in the practice or be seen outside the practice rather than wait several weeks to see their PCP for their healthcare needs. The lack of continuity of care has been associated with increased mortality, healthcare costs, and poorer health outcomes (AHRQ, 2013; Maarsingh, Henry, van de Ven, & Deeg, 2016). In addition to improving timely access, improved continuity of care must become a priority to improve health outcomes. According to the IHI (2019a), at least 80% of the patients seen by PCPs in a month should be their own empaneled patients (versus another PCPs). This business plan's proposed clinic scheduling template may help to increase its continuity of care percentage from 70% to 80%.

The problem of timely access to care and the lack of continuity are negatively affected by factors such as a shortage of providers, ineffective clinic processes, an increased need for appointments by newly insured patients seeking care, an aging and medically complex population, and poor communication between provider and patient. However, timely access and continuity of care may be positively affected by systems thinking and systems redesign with patient-centered care as the focus. These may include EHR redesign, clinic redesign, scheduling redesign, team-based and or continuity of care, and improved communication between the clinic and patients especially regarding their health concerns.

The solution to providing timely access and continuity of care involves a multifactorial approach and may be different for each organization based on its patient demographics and needs. Use of the third next available appointment as a marker for

timely access and having greater than 80% of the PCP's daily schedule filled with empaneled patients can be helpful in measuring access across the board in primary care practices. Based on this business plan, the proposed clinic will implement a new provider scheduling template to improve timely access and continuity of care in a FQHC. The goal for the new scheduling template will be to reduce the third next available to less than 14 days and improve continuity of care so that each provider is seeing at least 80% of their own patients every month. The business plan includes a plan for monitoring specific metrics to track the change to assess its effectiveness in improving timely access and continuity of care.

Estimating Scheduling Needs and Proposing a Scheduling Template

Rossi and Balasubramanian (2018) conducted a retrospective study to examine the panel size and availability of appointments for a theoretical full-time PCP seeing patients five days a week and working 40 hours per week. They sampled a Medicare population of 2,000 patients aged 65 years and older from the 2011 Medical Expenditure Panel Survey (MEPS) conducted by the AHRQ (2019). The MEPS surveyed patients as well as both private and public insurance companies to estimate their needs for access.

The Medicare population in Rossi and Balasubramanian's (2018) study required 157 appointments per week on average for PCPs with a panel size of 2,000. The need for access was averaged over five days in which each PCP would need to see at least 31 patients per day. The authors suggested having 1.68 PCPs per 2,000 Medicare patients to meet the average of 157 available appointments per week. Medicare patients used four times more home-health appointments than the general population and 1.5 times more specialty, inpatient, and outpatient resources than the general population. The need for

access in this business plan's clinic population may be similar to Rossi and Balasubramanian's (2018) Medicare sample. The Medicaid population is low-income and may have increased needs based on their SDOH, or the socioeconomic and political factors which may affect health (Mason et al., 2016). It is estimated that the SDOH can affect up to 80% of the health outcomes for each patient making timely access in this business plan's clinic population a priority (Manatt, Phelps, & Phillips, 2019).

Rossi and Balasubramanian's (2018) Medicare population needed an average of 157 weekly appointments per PCP. The clinic in this business plan is not able to offer 157 weekly appointments per PCP. However, Rossi and Balasubramanian (2018) did not base their estimate of need for appointments on a clinic that used 4 FTE staff per PCP. It is possible that patients could have had their needs addressed by staff other than PCPs, such as nurses, dietitians, and counselors, which can free up a PCP for additional appointments. An ideal scheduling process is still needed to manage the overflow of patients that is likely to occur in this proposed clinic setting that may lead to less timely access and decreased continuity of care.

Six Sigma

Literature was limited in the area of timely access, continuity of care, and the use of Six Sigma. Vest and Gamm (2009) conducted a systematic review on the effectiveness of several quality improvement methods, one being Six Sigma. Vest and Gamm (2009) evaluated nine studies designed to improve health care, but only one addressed timely access. That study took place in an obstetrics facility and was the only one to use a control group. Although there were issues with validity in the studies, all nine showed improvement in outcomes from use of Six Sigma. Hung, Harrison, Martinez, and Luft,

(2017) used Lean Six Sigma methodology to remodel their outpatient clinic system and did see improvement in efficiency and productivity, but patient surveys revealed patients' perceptions of less time spent with clinicians, for which they recommended further research.

In 2004, Revere, Black, and Huq described how Six Sigma had not been used as often in health care as in other industries, such as parts or car production, but that its focus on decreasing errors had the potential to be helpful in health care. The authors mention how sigma levels may be used to track improvement in medication errors. For the purposes of this project, sigma levels will not be used. Revere et al. (2004) acknowledged difficulties that organizations might encounter when transitioning from a current continuous quality improvement model, such as the Donabedian model of structure, process, and outcome (or whatever the organization currently uses), to the Six Sigma model. Instead, the authors proposed integrating Six Sigma into the organization's current continuous quality improvement methods, which may facilitate improvement with less of a cultural shift. The author's organization currently uses the Model for Improvement (Langley et al., 2009). However, the organization has started to incorporate the Lean Six Sigma methodology with the guidance of Six Sigma Black Belts to determine where to focus redesign of the organization to decrease defects, improve efficiency, and increase value for patients.

Kutz et al. (2018) used a pre and post-intervention mixed framework to improve their clinic work flows in an effort to address diabetic A1C targets. Kutz et al. successfully used the Six Sigma integrated approach that Revere et al. (2004) recommended by incorporating Lean Six Sigma with change and risk management

strategies. Kutz et al. also used the EHR to improve their workflows, which helped them achieve their diabetic A1C targets, another example of systems redesigns to improve patient-centered care.

Conclusions

This review of literature summarized the information related to factors affecting timely access to care and continuity of care and how the use of systems redesign and quality improvement with a patient centered approach can improve timely access to care and continuity of care. The literature was primarily focused on quality improvement projects with limited high-quality empiric studies. Several studies identified the lack of timely access as interfering with continuity of care in the primary care setting (Hollander & Kadlec, 2015; Hussey et al., 2014; Kohnke & Zielinski, 2017; Maarsingh et al., 2016; Shin et al., 2014). Additionally, the lack of timely access can result in poor patient satisfaction and organizational outcomes, including increased risk of patient mortality and increased cost of care (AHRQ, 2013; Maarsingh, Henry, van de Ven, & Deeg, 2016).

To improve timely access and continuity of care, systems redesign may be necessary, but timely access and improved continuity of care can be incrementally addressed by smaller patient-centered changes at the clinic level (Brandenburg et al., 2015). Six Sigma has been shown to help improve outcomes when applied to healthcare-specific endeavors (Vest & Gamm, 2009). By implementing a change in the provider scheduling template based on estimated patient need and improved daily clinic supply for appointments (Rossi & Balasubramanian, 2018), the clinic may be able to improve timely access to care and continuity in an area of high need.

BUSINESS PLAN

The purpose of this project is to create a business plan for the development of a scheduling plan for an FQHC to optimize timely access and continuity of care for an underserved population in Sandoval County, New Mexico. This business plan will incorporate Six Sigma methodology to guide the creation of a scheduling, staffing, and access model to achieve the goals of third next appointment within 14 days and to provide 80% continuity of care with patients' PCP. Although the business plan and budget were designed based on data from one clinic, it could be modified for implementation in other locations and settings. A balance sheet was developed to provide an estimate of the clinic's costs and projected revenue based on county demographic data (Appendix A).

Contextual Elements

This business plan proposes a scheduling plan for an FQHC in Sandoval County. The clinic will provide primary care services for a population mostly utilizing state insurance called Centennial Care in New Mexico or who are underinsured or uninsured altogether. Using Sandoval County as an example, this plan proposes a scheduling process that will maximize clinic efficiency and achieve timely access and continuity of care for patients. As recommended by Patel et al. (2013), this business plan proposes the use of 4 full time equivalent staff (FTEs) members per medical provider empaneled with 2,000 patients. This is an increase above the average 2.68 staff per medical provider used at most clinic settings in the United States.

New Sandoval County FQHC

Clinic Set-Up

The proposed set-up for the clinic includes a 20,000 square feet building which will have 14 exam rooms, 10 offices, four bathrooms, one large meeting space for staff and patient meetings, a staff kitchen and lunchroom, a large server room, and two large reception rooms. The lobby will have two associated waiting areas for patients to check in. The reception and waiting areas will be connected to three pod areas, with six exam rooms that connect off each pod.

The value stream map conducted at another clinic site determined that there should be at least two to three exam rooms per provider to reduce patient time in the waiting room (Curran-Meuli, 2013). The three open pods will each be surrounded by six exam rooms which provide a co-location for staff and providers. The co-location allows staff and medical providers to be near each other when providing patient care (Novotny, 2017). The co-location of two providers and four medical assistants (MAs) per pod has been shown to cut down on wait times for patients, improve team-based learning, and team morale (Novotny, 2017). Labs will be drawn by the MAs in the exam rooms and X-rays can be completed at a separate site a few miles away.

Clinic Staff

This business plan proposes 24 staff members in addition to the six medical providers based on recommended staffing inclusive of coordinators and other patient support who can manage patient care and other administrative tasks. The staffing ratio allows providers increased direct patient care (Peikes et al., 2014). The project clinic staff should consist of 12 MAs, one health educator, three front desk clerks, one patient

services representative, two case managers, one dietitian, one clinic manager, one clinic supervisor, and two RNs. The two case managers will be hired as licensed social workers who will serve as behavioral health therapists.

Proposed Budget

A balance sheet was created to estimate costs for this business plan's proposed clinic (Appendix A). Estimates were based on a market analysis for the area and on personal experience in clinic settings. The business plan's clinic is located in a hot spot or area of unmet need as identified by the Health Resources and Services Administration (HRSA, 2019). The proposed clinic is expected to qualify for a grant which pays up to one million dollars as a new healthcare site in an area of need. The clinic will receive \$300,000 from local investors. Therefore, total investments will be \$1,300,000.

As estimated by the State of New Mexico HSD (2019), the per-member per-month (PMPM) estimate for this clinic is approximately \$660. This dollar amount falls somewhere between New Mexico's PMPM Medicaid waiver (\$526) and non-waiver (\$724) eligible members. Medicaid waivers allow states to cover services for otherwise ineligible members based on certain demographics for provider services such as long-term care (Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services, 2018). Given that the clinic will serve 12,000 patients, it is anticipated that the assets from the PMPM will total \$7,920,000.

The fixed expenses were estimated to include \$95,000 for office equipment, office furniture, and exam room furniture. Leasehold improvements are any changes made to the leased building by the renter, such as installing new carpet, creating rooms and sections, and painting (University of Michigan Finance, 2019). The clinic will

require leasehold improvements to accommodate the reception area, waiting rooms with connected pods, and six exam rooms. The amount estimated for the improvements is \$100,000 for the first year of practice. The total assets expected in the first year from PMPM are \$7,920,000, \$1,000,000 from a HRSA grant, and \$300,000 from local investors. The office equipment, office furniture, exam room furniture, and leasehold improvements, and office furnishings will increase assets by \$195,000, thus bringing the total assets value to \$9,415,000.

Clinic Liabilities

The current liabilities include salaries, benefits, worker's compensation, income tax payable, office supplies, medical supplies, and electronic medical record (EMR). The total amount anticipated for salaries is estimated to be \$1,806,500 based on a review of salaries from glassdoor.com, the New Mexico Department of Health, and the University of New Mexico websites. The salaries for all staff were averaged at the higher end of salaries from online job postings. The proposed FQHC for this business plan will contribute 25% towards employees' benefits; therefore, the cost of benefits for the organization will be \$451,625. In 2014, the National Academy of Social Insurance (2016) stated that New Mexico's workers compensation insurance costs employers \$1.44 for every \$100 in salary. The employer contribution towards worker's compensation for 30 employees in this business plan will be \$2,601,360. The current Medicare tax rate is 1.45% and the current Social Security tax rate is 6.2% (Josephson, 2017). The total Federal Insurance Contributions Act tax rate is 7.65%. Therefore, income tax payable by the company is estimated to be \$3,956,910. The office equipment and supplies estimate is \$6,000 which includes a cost of \$200 per employee (there are 30 employees) per year

(LAC Group, 2014). The medical supplies estimate of \$45,000 is based on an examination of Tigermedical.com, a medical supply website. The EMR cost estimate for a five-provider practice can reach upwards of \$162,000 for the purchase and \$85,500 for maintenance in the first year of practice totaling \$247,500 (Fleming, Culler, McCorkle, Becker, & Ballard, 2011). The mortgage lease payable includes operational and janitorial costs. The building is 20,000 square feet, which rents for \$15 per square foot, per year. Therefore, the mortgage lease payable will be \$300,000. The total liabilities are expected to be \$9,414,895. The total positive remaining balance between the total assets (\$9,415,000) and liabilities (\$9,414,895) will be \$105.

Fiscal Projections and Estimating Patient Requests for Access

Considering Rossi and Balasubramanian's (2018) study, one full-time provider empaneled with 2,000 general patients may see 18 or 19 patients per day, provided each patient visit is 20 minutes in length. According to the Medscape Physician Compensation Report (Kane, 2019), physicians spent 16 minutes on average with their patients. Lichtenstein (2016) found a subset of patients at Harvard who were considered medically complex. They spent more time with the physician discussing their medication regimen, behavioral health needs, and coordination of care related to specialty compared to less complex patients. Physicians were less likely to have spent time addressing appropriate screening based on current guidelines or providing education with the more medically complex patients compared to the less medical complex patients. More time spent with medically complex patients may be necessary for comprehensive patient care, therefore, this business plan has allowed 20-minute visits per patient and 40 minutes per patients for ER and hospital follow up appointments.

An eight-hour workday from 8 AM to 5 PM with a one-hour lunch has the potential to provide 24 patient appointments. If each appointment is 20 minutes in length, and each provider has one hour of administrative time in each workday, there will be 21 appointments per day or 105 appointments per week per PCP. In one week, the PCPs may have 10 ER follow-ups (two per day) and up to five hospital follow-ups, or one per day (Rossi & Balasubramanian, 2018). The ER and hospital follow-ups will be scheduled as 40-minute visits. This reduces the available patient appointments on any given day from 21 to 15. Each provider will typically receive 15 calls per day for access, but some of these could be due to requests for ER or hospital follow-ups.

For this business plan's proposed scheduling template, it can be assumed that each provider receives approximately 12 calls per day for access (15 minus three calls a day for either ER or a hospital follow-up appointment requests). Due to the long wait times for patients who are new to the practice, one appointment on each provider's schedule will be held for schedulers to place new patients in the afternoon of each day. This will bring down the available appointments per provider from 15 to 14. One of the calls for new patient access is included in the remaining 12 calls per day for access requiring the clinic to find access appointments for 11 more calls for access per provider per day.

Kheirkhah, Feng, Travis, Tavakoli-Tabasi, and Sharafkhaneh (2016) estimated the no-show rates for 10 Veterans Affairs hospital outpatient clinics, including rural and urban settings, was 19%. One community health clinic serving a high percentage of Medicaid-insured patients found its no-show rate to be 16.5% (Kaplan-Lewis & Percac-

Lima, 2013). The proposed clinic has an anticipated a no-show rate of 23%, which is one of the higher no-show rates in the area.

No-shows may occur more often when the next available appointment is extended farther out (Medical Group Management Association, 2017). No-shows lead to revenue loss (Smith, 2018). Smith (2018) found that, in an academic clinic serving an urban population, each no-show resulted in a loss of \$62. If the providers in this business plan setting are scheduled to see 21 patients per day, a 23% no-show rate is equivalent to five no-shows per day or a loss of \$310 per day per provider. In a year, the clinic could lose up to \$483,600 for all six providers due to no-shows. This business plan's proposed scheduling template may be able to save clinic money in addition to improving timely access and continuity of care.

Provider Scheduling Template

The goal of this project is to improve access and continuity, and this can be done with a new scheduling template. In accordance with the New Mexico's HSD (2014), urgent symptomatic appointments must be seen within 24 hours, non-urgent symptomatic appointments must be seen within 14 days, and routine symptomatic appointments must be seen within 30 days of the access request. Because of these stipulations, each provider who now has 14 available appointments per day will be asked to leave half of those appointments as open access appointments, specifically for their empaneled patients calling for access. Three open access appointments will be available in the morning with four open access appointments available in the afternoon. Open access appointments are appointments that are opened the day the patient's call in for access (Murray & Berwick, 2003). Open access appointments help organizations provide appointment availability the

day the patient seeks care (Murray & Berwick, 2003). Murray and Berwick (2003) refer to open access scheduling as helping providers stay ahead of patient care by “doing today’s work, today” (p. 1037).

Define (DMAIC)

The clinic’s total patient population is 12,000 and the clinic must meet the needs for timely access to care and continuity of care. This business plan’s proposed provider scheduling template will have seven of the remaining 14 open appointments saved for open access each day. This should accommodate at least seven of the 11 remaining calls for access per day, leaving four remaining calls to be addressed per day. With this scheduling template, each day should have two ER (one in the morning and one in the afternoon) and one hospital follow-up in the afternoon, each 40 minutes in length. It will also include one 20-minute new patient appointment in the afternoon, and seven open access appointments (three in the morning and four in the afternoon). This leaves seven appointments (three in the morning and four in the afternoon) open on each PCP’s template for the clinic to schedule an empaneled patient routine follow-up appointment and which will likely already be taken by the day of the appointment. The remaining four calls per day per provider for access still needs to be accommodated. Same-day access calls from patients whose PCP is already booked for the day will be forwarded to their PCP to determine when and with whom the patient should be scheduled. Given the high no-show rate predicted for this clinic, providers could opt to double book any request per day, but this is not expected. It is expected that, as long as providers are not out of the clinic, most of the clinic’s access and continuity goals should be met. The no-show rate

will be addressed in a future quality improvement project in order to further improve the clinic's efficiency and eliminate defects in the clinic.

Each of the six providers will work Monday through Friday. However, each provider must work at least two days of the week from 11 AM to 8 PM while the remaining three days can be 8 AM to 5 PM (see Table 1). This type of scheduling provides the patients and the clinic opportunities to arrange transportation to and from their appointments and can hopefully allow for improved access and continuity of care with the PCP.

Measure (DMAIC)

A family of measures as recommended by the IHI (2019c) will be used to evaluate the new scheduling procedure (see Appendix B). The six measures include two outcome measures, two process measures, and two balancing measures. The family of measures will assist in clarifying what is being measured, whether the practice change has resulted in significant changes, and if there have been unintended effects (IHI, 2019c). According to the IHI (2019c), outcome measures are monitored during the project to assess the practice change. The process measures are related to the fidelity of the business plan to improve the scheduling procedure. The balancing measure is used to monitor unintended consequences of the intervention (Langley et al., 2009).

Table 1

PCP Scheduling Template

Appointment #	Appointment Time (8 AM to 5 PM)	Appointment Time (11 AM to 8 PM)	Type of appointment	Appointment Length
1	8:00 AM	11:00 AM	Routine Follow Up	20 Minutes
2	8:20 AM	11:20 AM	ER Follow Up #1	40 Minutes
3	9:00 AM	12:00 PM	Open Access #1	20 Minutes
4	9:20 AM	12:20 PM	Open Access #2	20 Minutes
Administrative Time (20 Minutes)	9:40 AM	12:40 PM	Administrative Time (20 Minutes)	Administrative Time (20 Minutes)
5	10:00 AM	1:00 PM	Routine Follow Up	20 Minutes
6	10:20 AM	1:20 PM	Routine Follow Up	20 Minutes
7	10:40 AM	1:40 PM	Open Access	20 Minutes
Lunch (1 Hour)	11:00 PM	02:00 PM	Lunch (1 Hour)	Lunch (1 Hour)
8	12:00 PM	3:00 PM	Open Access	20 Minutes
9	12:20 PM	03:20 PM	Routine Follow Up	20 Minutes
10	12:40 PM	3:40 PM	Routine Follow Up	20 Minutes
11	1:00 PM	4:00 PM	Routine Follow Up	20 Minutes
12	1:20 PM	4:20 PM	Open Access	20 Minutes
13	1:40 PM	4:40 PM	ER Follow Up #2	40 Minutes
14	2:20 PM	5:20 PM	Routine Follow Up	20 Minutes
15	2:40 PM	5:40 PM	Hospital Follow Up	40 Minutes
16	3:20 PM	6:20 PM	Open Access	20 Minutes
17	3:40 PM	6:40 PM	New Patient	20 Minutes
18	4:00 PM	7:00 PM	Open Access	20 Minutes
Administrative Time (20 Minutes)	4:20 PM	7:20 PM	Administrative Time (20 Minutes)	Administrative Time (20 Minutes)
Administrative Time (20 Minutes)	4:40 PM	7:40 PM	Administrative Time (20 Minutes)	Administrative Time (20 Minutes)
END	5 PM	8 PM	END	END

The first outcome measure is the number of days to the third next available appointment for a routine physical with the PCP, with 14 days as the goal. This will assess performance related to access. The second outcome measure is the percentage of patients seen by the PCP who were empaneled to the PCP. This will assess performance related to continuity. The first process measure is the total number of open access appointments available at the beginning of each day. There should be seven open access appointments for the PCP every day. This will inform the project's author as to whether the open access appointments are being used prematurely by staff to schedule patients. The second process measure will be the total number of appointment requests daily, for the same PCP. The first balancing measure will be the PCP's productivity, which should be 2.9 patients per hour. The second balancing measure will be the total number of patients empaneled to the same PCP each month. This project will focus mainly on measures related to one PCP and their empaneled patients.

Access: Third Next Available Appointment for a Routine Physical with the PCP (Outcome Measure # 1)

The third next available appointment for a routine physical exam is defined by the IHI (2019b) as the average number of days between when a patient requests an appointment with their PCP and the third next available appointment for a routine physical exam, a new patient seeking a physical exam, or a routine follow-up. For this business plan, the author will use the number of days between when the patient called to schedule an appointment and the third next available appointment for a routine physical exam. This is a primary outcome measure because it is typically the last appointment to be offered urgently at the author's clinic. The first and second next available

appointments do not count as true access because they are typically available due to cancellations.

This business plan's PCP's current wait time for the third next available routine physical appointment is currently 21 days. The business plan's clinic would like to reduce the third next available for a routine physical from 21 days to 14 days; therefore, the goal for this scheduling template modification project is a 33% reduction in wait time for the third next available for the PCP over the six-month practice change. On Wednesdays at 8 AM, the MA will write down the current date, then document the date of the third next available appointment for the PCP of focus for a routine physical. The number of days will be calculated based on the difference between today's date and the date of the first available. This number of days will be the data points. This information will be stored on a password-protected spreadsheet. Baseline data will need to be collected from January 2020 through June 2020. The data will be placed on a run chart and then converted to an I chart once 20 data points are gathered.

Continuity: Patients Empaneled to and Seen by the PCP (Outcome Measure #2)

Continuity of care is the patient's ability to see their PCP when they schedule an appointment (Maarsingh et al., 2016). According to the IHI (2019a), when patients schedule an appointment, they should see their PCP at least 80% of the time. In this business plan, continuity of care will be measured by reviewing the schedule of the PCP of focus one day a week to determine the percentage of the PCP's assigned empaneled patients seen by that provider. Every Wednesday at 5 PM, the MA will review the same PCP's schedule and write down the current date, the last three digits of the patient's medical record number (MRN), and whether the patients seen were empaneled to the

PCP. This information will be stored on the password-protected spreadsheet. The last three digits of the patient's MRN will be used to track which patients were seen by their PCP. Continuity of care percentage will be derived by dividing the total number of patients seen by the assigned PCP that day (Wednesday) by the total number of patients scheduled that day and multiplying this result by 100. Baseline data will need to be collected from January 2020 through June 2020. Data will be placed on a run chart and then converted to a P chart once 20 data points are gathered. Any patients scheduled with the PCP for a nurse visit will be excluded from this calculation.

The Number of Open Access Appointments Available Each Morning (Process Measure #1)

To ensure the process of practice change is occurring, the number of open access appointments on the PCP's schedule will need to be followed every day. Every morning, the MA will check the same PCP's schedule, count the total number of available open access appointments, and document the total number on the password-protected spreadsheet. Baseline data will be collected from January 2020 through June 2020. Data will be placed on a run chart and converted to a C chart once 20 data points are collected.

The Total Number of Daily Appointment Requests per PCP (Process Measure #2)

A second process measure will be to determine how many visits are delayed or are not seen the same day patients seek access. Each staff member will keep a running record each day of how many patient requests for an appointment with the PCP of focus were made. Every day by 5 PM, the MA will review the running record for the same PCP and write down the total number of requests for access that occurred that day. This information will be stored on the password-protected spreadsheet. Prior to

commencement of this business plan, baseline data were collected for the number of requests for same-day access. Data will be placed on a run chart and converted to a C chart once 20 data points are collected.

PCP's Empaneled Productivity (Balancing Measure #1)

Productivity of the PCP may be affected through an increase or a decrease in the number of appointments scheduled. This measure will track the empaneled productivity of the PCP of focus. On Fridays at 5 PM, the MA will review the PCP's schedule for the week and write down the current date, the last three digits of the patient's MRN, and whether each patient was empaneled to the PCP. This information will be stored on the password-protected spreadsheet. Baseline data will need to be collected from January 2020 through June 2020. The project author will calculate the PCP's average weekly productivity by dividing the total number of empaneled patients seen by the PCP by the total number of patient care hours (which should be 35 hours due to one hour of daily administration time unless the PCP was out). The PCP's productivity is expected to be 2.9 patients per hour. The PCP's average weekly empaneled productivity will be placed on a run chart and then converted to an I chart once 20 data points are gathered.

PCP's Monthly Empanelment Size (Balancing Measure #2)

The PCP's monthly empanelment (or the total number of the PCP's assigned patients per month) will be followed during the project. The number of empaneled patients may increase or decrease during the project, which may affect patients' timely access to care with their PCP, continuity of care with their PCP, and provider productivity. Once a month, the clinic manager will run a report that will calculate the number of empaneled patients for the PCP of focus. Baseline data will be collected from

January 2020 through June 2020. The number of empaneled patients for the PCP will be placed on a run chart and then converted to a C chart once 12 data points are gathered.

Analyze (DMAIC)

In the analyze stage of DMAIC, run and control charts should be used to analyze processes for stability (Provost & Murray, 2011; Kubiak, 2014). These charts will begin with 20 data points of baseline data and will then be followed as the new scheduling template is implemented to determine whether there is improvement. A mockup of control charts for each of the measures demonstrating simulated pre and post implementation results are shown in Figures 4 to 6. The various control charts below were selected based on recommendations by Provost and Murray (2011).

The third next available appointment in days for a routine physical will be followed on an I chart once 12 data points are gathered (Figure 3). It is anticipated that the PCP's third next available appointment for a routine physical will decrease during the project with implementation of a new provider scheduling template.

Figure 3. I chart for third next available appointment and provider productivity. The I chart is for outcome measure #1 (number of days to the third next available) and balancing measure #2 (PCP's productivity) with fictional data. If this were true baseline data for this project, non-random variation or an unstable process is indicated.

The continuity of care with the PCP will be followed on a P chart once 20 data points are gathered (Figure 4). It is anticipated that the continuity of care with the PCP will increase during the project, since patients will be given more access to their PCP. The no-show rate will be followed on a P chart once 20 data points are gathered (Figure 4). It is anticipated that the no-show rate will improve along with the third next available appointment due to the new provider scheduling template.

Figure 4. P chart for continuity of care. The P chart is for outcome measure #2 (continuity of care) with fictional data. If this were true baseline data for this project, the continuity of care percentage would be considered a stable process as most of the data points hug the control limit (CL).

The number of open access appointments available each morning and the daily total number of appointment requests for the PCP of focus will be followed on a C chart once 20 data points are gathered (Figure 5). It is anticipated that the total number of open access appointments available each morning will be at least 7, which would indicate a stable process. It is anticipated that the total number of requests made daily by patients for appointments for each PCP will not increase and may potentially decrease due to improved access via the new scheduling template.

Figure 5. C chart for the number of open access appointments, daily PCP open appointments, and PCP’s monthly empanelment size. The C chart is for process measure #1 (number of open access appointments available at the beginning of each day for the PCP), process measure #2 (daily total number of appointment requests for the PCP), and balancing measure #2 (PCP’s monthly empanelment) with fictional data. If this were true baseline data for this project, the average number of open access requests for appointments would be considered a stable process as most of the data points hug the control limit (CL).

The PCP’s productivity (balancing measure #1) will be followed on an I chart once 20 data points are gathered (Figure 3). It is anticipated that the PCP’s productivity will not decrease and may potentially increase during the project, since it is anticipated that the no-show rate may improve, leading to more patients being seen. The monthly PCP’s empanelment size will be followed on a C chart once 12 data points are gathered (Figure 5). The PCP’s empanelment size may grow or decrease during the project due to changes in scheduling.

Improve (DMAIC)

Clinic Scheduling Process

Most of the PCPs in the project clinic have a third next available appointment for routine physicals with a three- to six-week wait period. The clinic would like the third next available appointment for a routine physical for any PCP to be two weeks or less.

The third next available for a routine physical may be extended due to PCP unavailability or patients are in settings where there are not enough providers to care for the number of patients seeking care (Murray & Berwick, 2003). When patients seek same-day access, but their PCP is not available, the patient is typically scheduled with another PCP in the clinic. When patients are scheduled with a provider they are not assigned to, the project clinic refers to the occurrence as patient overflow. At the project clinic, there is patient overflow every day. The lack of continuity the day the patient seeks access with their PCP frequently results in another needed follow-up appointment with their PCP, contributing to the extended third next available appointment problem.

The project's organization went through a value stream map at another clinic location which showed an increased amount of nonvalue added from the time patients seek access through calling the office, checking in at the clinic, and as they flowed through the clinic for their visit. The processes that patients utilize for accessing and navigating care are similar across the organization. The proposed scheduling intervention is based on the other clinic site's value stream map results.

Currently, patients call into a centralized location to schedule appointments with their PCP. The patients are queried about why they are requesting an appointment. If there are any symptoms suggesting urgency, the patients are transferred directly to their local clinic nurse for triage. If patients are having any emergent symptoms, they are directed to call 911. The nurse triages the patients and determines if they should call 911, head directly to the emergency department, or come immediately to the clinic. Because of the long phone wait times and reduced access, patients tend to walk into the clinics asking to be seen, which can burden an already overworked system.

Patients who walk in for access and are not deemed emergent but request a follow-up appointment will be scheduled according to the nature of their need, using the timely access regulations of the New Mexico HSD (2014). If the patients are established with one of the six PCPs, meaning they are not new patients, they will be offered the first available appointment with their PCP, which may be several weeks away. If the patients request an earlier appointment, they will then be scheduled with any other available PCP, sometimes at other locations in the organization, which may be farther from their residence. Patients may email their provider requesting an appointment and, sometimes, the PCP may double book or defer the need to another provider if the patient cannot be seen by them that day.

Currently, patients of the business plan's clinic may wait three to six weeks for a routine physical appointment, which is the third next available appointment for a routine physical. When patients are delayed by three weeks, it prolongs their care, may increase unnecessary ER visits in the surrounding areas, and can increase or interrupt the workload for other providers at the business plan's clinic including triage nurses and clerical staff (Murray & Berwick, 2003).

Control (DMAIC)

Post project implementation, data will still be monitored through the use of control charts to assess whether improvements are being maintained (reflecting a stable process). Data will be collected monthly post project implementation. If any processes destabilize, there must be intervention at the clinic level to determine why the process has destabilized and to assess what can be done to make the process stable again. Often,

processes may destabilize after implementation because processes were not put in place to support maintenance of the change such as new policies (Provost & Murray, 2011).

DISCUSSION

The proposed clinic will be new and has the benefit of more FTEs per PCP than many clinics in the country. In addition to increased FTEs, the new proposed provider scheduling template and clinic layout should help increase the clinic's patients' timely access and continuity of care. There may be a possibility to increase the amount of time spent with each patient, in order to provide comprehensive care to the medically complex population common to Sandoval County.

This business plan could help increase the clinic's revenue if it is successful. The clinic should consider following how many visits are performed collaboratively with the clinic nurses and the clinic dietician health educators. These visits are billable in some cases and with increased revenue can help the clinic advocate for additional support in the future, based on the data. The number of referrals for psychiatry to an outside clinic or for psychiatric emergency services from the clinic's behavioral health providers should be assessed, as it may document a need for an embedded clinic psychiatrist.

The clinic opted to not include a pharmacy/pharmacist due to licensing requirements. However, future endeavors may include the addition of a pharmacist. Pharmacists can help alleviate some of the need for visits with the PCP by seeing patients for medication titration, reconciling medications in patients experiencing polypharmacy, educating patients regarding their medications, or administering vaccinations.

Ideally, patient satisfaction should be monitored during any proposed change to the clinic's processes as a balancing measure; however, because the patient satisfaction data are collected quarterly by the organization, the data will likely not become available until after the project's completion. Further evaluation of the intervention using patient

satisfaction as a balancing measure could be considered when deciding to implement the plan organization-wide. Lastly, the no-show rate was not included as a measure since the clinic is newly proposed, but there are plans to include it in subsequent iterations of quality improvement.

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APPENDIX A
BALANCE SHEET

Balance Sheet	
Assets	
Current assets:	Current year
Per Member Per Month	7,920,000.00
Investments	1,300,000.00
Other	-
Total current assets	9,220,000.00
Fixed assets:	Current year
Office and Exam Room Furniture	95,000.00
Leasehold Improvements	100,000.00
Total fixed assets	195,000.00
Total assets	9,415,000.00
Liabilities and owner's equity	
Current liabilities:	Current year
Salaries	1,806,500.00
Benefits	451,625.00
Income tax payable	3,956,910.00
Worker's Compensation	2,601,360.00
Office Supplies	6,000.00
Medical Supplies	45,000.00
Electronic Medical Record	247,500.00
Total current liabilities	9,114,895.00
Long-term liabilities:	Previous year
Mortgage/lease payable	300,000
Total liabilities	9,414,895.00
Balance	105.00

APPENDIX B

FAMILY OF MEASURES

Type	Measure	How collected	Subgroup	Type of Chart
Outcome	1. 3 rd next appointment for routine physical	Wednesdays at 8 am, the MA will check the PCP's schedule, document the date data was collected and the date of the 3 rd next available appointment for a routine physical. MA will document data on a spreadsheet by the end of the day.	Weekly	Run and I chart
	2. Continuity = % empaneled to and seen by PCP	Wednesdays at 5 PM, the MA will review the PCP's schedule, write down the last three numbers of each patient's medical record number (MRN) and whether the patient was empaneled to the PCP (and if not empaneled, then write down the PCP). MA will document data on a spreadsheet by the end of the day.	Weekly	Run and P chart
Process	1. The Number of Open Access Appointments Available Each Morning	Every morning by 8 AM, one MA will check the PCP's schedule and count the total # of open access appointments available. MA will document data on a spreadsheet by the end of the day.	Daily	Run and C chart
	2. Daily total number of appointment requests for the PCP	Staff will tally the total number of appointment requests for the	Daily	Run and C chart

Balancing	1.Provider productivity	PCP. Front desk will document data on a spreadsheet by the end of the day On Fridays at 5 PM, the MA will review the PCP's schedule for the week, write down the current date, the last three numbers of the MRN for each patient seen, whether each patient was empaneled to the PCP, and the total number of empaneled patients seen. MA will document data on a spreadsheet by the end of the day	Weekly	Run and I chart
	2.Number of PCP's monthly empaneled patients	Once a month, the clinic manager will run a report that will calculate the number of PCP's empaneled patients. Clinic manager will document the number on a spreadsheet by the end of the month	Monthly	Run and C chart
